

Conference Abstract

On the Sicilian cave dwelling species of Auchenorrhyncha (Insecta, Rhynchota)

Vera D'Urso[‡], Antonino Puglisi[‡]

[‡] Department of Biological, Geological and Environmental Sciences, University of Catania, Catania, Italy

Corresponding author: Vera D'Urso (dursove@unict.it)

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Abstract

Up to now, troglobitic Auchenorrhyncha identified for Europe outside of the Macaronesian region include two species belonging to the Cixiidae family. In this context, Sicily is a very interesting island because there are both limestone caves and lava tubes that allow the presence of at least two obligately cave dwelling species belonging to *Ibleocixius* D'Urso & Grasso 2009 and *Cixius* Latreilles 1804 genera. *Ibleocixius* is a troglobitic genus, endemic from Sicily with a unique species, *Ibleocixius dunae* D'Urso & Grasso 2009, living in a limestone cave of South-eastern Sicily. Recently, a new troglobitic taxon (under description) has been found in some lava tubes on the Etna volcano; it belongs to the genus *Cixius*, to the *C. pallipes-wagneri* group. Both species live on the roots that penetrate the caves. They have a different palaeogeographic history. *Ibleocixius dunae* is a paleoendemic taxon showing a strong degree of troglomorphy, and the genus differs from *Cixius* and related taxa in the different arrangement of several characters which are also present in other taxa. *Cixius* n.sp. is a neoendemic taxon showing morphological characters close to those of the epigeal species *Cixius wagneri* (Holzinger et al. 2003).

Keywords

Troglobitic species, Cixiidae, limestone caves, lava tubes, Sicily

Presenting author

Vera D'Urso

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References

- Holzinger WE, Kammerlander I, Nickel H (2003) The Auchenorrhyncha of Central Europe. Volume 1: Fulgoromorpha, Cicadomorpha excl. Cicadellidae. Brill, Leiden-Boston, 1-673 pp. [ISBN 9004128956]